

Cross-Paradigm Comparison of Industrial Surface Defect Segmentation: Supervised Networks, Zero-Shot Foundation Models, and Parameter-Efficient Fine-Tuning

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U. Dixit conceived the study, implemented all models, conducted experiments, and wrote the manuscript. S. Kumar contributed to the quantitative and qualitative analysis of results.

Abstract—Industrial surface defect segmentation is critical for automated quality control in manufacturing but remains challenging due to subtle defect appearances, extreme foreground–background class imbalance, and limited annotated data. This paper presents a systematic three-way comparison: (1) fully supervised specialist networks (U-Net and DeepLabV3+), (2) zero-shot inference with SAM2, and (3) SAM2 fine-tuned via Low-Rank Adaptation (LoRA). Experiments on the Magnetic Tile Defect Dataset [9] (1,344 images, five defect classes) show that SAM2+LoRA achieves the best mean IoU (0.2184) and Dice coefficient (0.2466), outperforming DeepLabV3+ (IoU = 0.1849) and U-Net (IoU = 0.0857), while training only 11.74 M parameters—25% of SAM2’s total. While absolute IoU values remain modest due to the small dataset (940 training images) and extreme class imbalance (defect pixels < 1% of image area), the relative improvements across paradigms are consistent and meaningful. Zero-shot SAM2 performs poorly (IoU = 0.0235), confirming a large domain gap between natural and industrial imagery. Grad-CAM visualisations show SAM2+LoRA localises defect regions more precisely than supervised counterparts.

Index Terms—surface defect segmentation, SAM2, LoRA, U-Net, DeepLabV3+, Grad-CAM, industrial inspection, parameter-efficient fine-tuning

I. INTRODUCTION

Industrial surface defect detection is a cornerstone of automated quality control in manufacturing sectors including steel, ceramic, and semiconductor production. Undetected defects can cause product failures, safety hazards, and significant economic losses. Pixel-level segmentation of defects enables fine-grained inspection but is substantially harder than classification or bounding-box detection.

The dominant approach has been fully supervised convolutional networks [1],[2] trained end-to-end on labelled defect images. These models face two key limitations: (i) they require large annotated datasets expensive to obtain in industrial settings, and (ii) they generalise poorly across defect types, materials, and acquisition conditions.

The emergence of vision foundation models, particularly the Segment Anything Model (SAM2) [5], introduced a new paradigm: zero-shot segmentation where a single model segments arbitrary objects given only point or bounding-box prompts. However, SAM2 was pretrained on natural images and industrial defects present unique challenges—subtle textures, small spatial extent, and fundamentally different visual statistics.

Parameter-efficient fine-tuning (PEFT) via Low-Rank Adaptation (LoRA) [6] offers a compelling middle ground: adapt a pretrained foundation model by training only low-rank weight updates, keeping the large backbone frozen. This preserves rich pretrained representations while drastically reducing data and compute requirements.

We present the first systematic three-way comparison of these paradigms on industrial defect segmentation, using a unified experimental setup and evaluation protocol, with Grad-CAM [7] visualisations for explainability. **Contributions:**

- A cross-paradigm benchmark on the 1,344-image Magnetic Tile Defect Dataset under a unified protocol.
- Empirical evidence that LoRA-adapted SAM2 outperforms both fully-supervised baselines while training only 25% of SAM2’s total parameters.
- Grad-CAM explainability analysis revealing qualitative differences in defect localisation across paradigms.
- Practical insights on the accuracy–speed–parameter trade-off for industrial deployment.

II. RELATED WORK

A. Industrial Defect Segmentation

U-Net [1], originally proposed for biomedical image segmentation, has been widely adopted for surface defect segmentation due to its encoder–decoder architecture with skip connections. DeepLabV3+ [2] employs atrous spatial pyramid pooling (ASPP) to capture multi-scale context. A key challenge is extreme class imbalance: defect pixels typically constitute less than 1% of the image area. Combined Dice–BCE loss functions [3] outperform standard cross-entropy in this regime.

B. Segment Anything Model

SAM [4] introduced a promptable segmentation framework trained on SA-1B (11M images, 1.1B masks). SAM2 [5] extends SAM to video with a Hiera transformer image encoder and streaming memory module. Its performance on specialised domains including industrial surfaces degrades significantly due to distribution shift.

C. Parameter-Efficient Fine-Tuning

LoRA [6] decomposes weight updates into low-rank matrices, enabling fine-tuning with a fraction of the parameters. Originally proposed for large language models, LoRA has been successfully applied to vision transformers for medical image segmentation [8]. To our knowledge, no prior work applies LoRA-based SAM2 adaptation to industrial defect segmentation within a systematic cross-paradigm comparison.

D. Explainability in Defect Detection

Grad-CAM [7] visualises class-discriminative regions by computing gradients of the target class score with respect to feature maps. In industrial inspection, explainability is critical for operator trust and regulatory compliance. Its application to segmentation models in a cross-paradigm context has not been studied.

III. METHOD

A. Problem Formulation

Given an input image x , we produce a binary segmentation mask where a value of 1 denotes a defect pixel. We evaluate three paradigms for learning or applying this mapping.

B. Supervised Specialist Networks

U-Net. Standard U-Net with encoder depth 4, base filter size 64, MaxPool downsampling, and transposed convolution upsampling. Skip connections concatenate encoder and decoder features at each level.

DeepLabV3+. ResNet-50 backbone pretrained on ImageNet with Layer4 modified to use dilated convolutions (dilation=2, stride=1). ASPP module uses atrous rates {6,12,18}. Lightweight decoder fuses ASPP features (256-dim) with low-level features from Layer1 (projected to 48-dim).

Training. Both models trained with AdamW (lr=3e-4, weight decay=1e-4) and CosineAnnealingLR for 50 epochs, batch size 8, mixed precision (FP16). Combined Dice-BCE loss: $\mathcal{L} = 0.5 \times \text{Dice} + 0.5 \times \text{BCE}$. All experiments use fixed random seed 42; results represent single-run evaluations due to compute constraints.

C. SAM2 Zero-Shot Inference

SAM2.1-Small (Hiera backbone, 46.1M parameters) with automatic mask generator. A 16×16 grid of point prompts produces candidate masks; those with predicted IoU below 0.7 are discarded. The highest-scoring mask is taken as the defect segmentation. No fine-tuning is performed.

D. SAM2 + LoRA

LoRA injection. LoRA modules injected into all multi-head attention projections (Q, K, V, output) in SAM2's mask decoder with rank $r = 4$ and scaling $\alpha = 8$. The image encoder is fully frozen; mask decoder and prompt encoder are trainable, yielding 11.74M trainable parameters (25% of SAM2's total 46.1M).

Training. $n = 5$ foreground points sampled from ground-truth mask per image. AdamW (lr = 1e-4), CosineAnnealingLR, 40 epochs, same Dice-BCE loss, gradient clipping (max norm 1.0). Inference uses $n = 3$ test-time points; logit map thresholded at 0.

E. Grad-CAM Visualisation

For U-Net and DeepLabV3+, Grad-CAM targets the last decoder feature map using standard gradient weighting. For SAM2+LoRA, the L2-norm of image encoder embeddings serves as a feature attribution proxy, consistent with transformer visualisation literature [7]. Heatmap overlaid on input image with $\alpha = 0.55$.

IV. EXPERIMENTS

A. Dataset

Magnetic Tile Defect Dataset [9]: 1,344 RGB images, five defect categories (Blowhole 115, Break 85, Crack 57, Fray 32, Uneven 103) plus 952 defect-free images, each with binary segmentation mask. All images resized to 256×256. Split: 70% train (940), 15% val (202), 15% test (202), fixed seed 42. Training augmentation: horizontal flip, vertical flip, random 90° rotation, colour jitter (brightness/contrast ± 0.2).

B. Evaluation Metrics

- Mean IoU (mIoU): $\text{TP}/(\text{TP}+\text{FP}+\text{FN})$
- Dice coefficient: $2\text{TP}/(2\text{TP}+\text{FP}+\text{FN})$
- FPS: single-image inference on NVIDIA T4 GPU
- Trainable Params: parameters updated during training (distinct from total model parameters)
- Size (MB): checkpoint file size on disk

C. Implementation Details

All experiments use PyTorch on a single NVIDIA T4 GPU (16 GB VRAM). SAM2.1-Small weights initialised from the official checkpoint. Batch size 8 for supervised models; SAM2+LoRA processes one image at a time due to the prompt-based training paradigm.

TABLE I — QUANTITATIVE COMPARISON ON MAGNETIC TILE DEFECT DATASET (TEST SET, 202 IMAGES). † = TRAINABLE PARAMETERS ONLY; SAM2 TOTAL = 46.1 M.

Model	IoU \uparrow	Dice \uparrow	FPS \uparrow	Train Params	Total Params	Size MB
U-Net (supervised)	0.0857	0.1186	47.3	31.0 M	31.0 M	124.2
DeepLabV3+ (supervised)	0.1849	0.2162	43.7	40.3 M	40.3 M	161.7
SAM2 (zero-shot)	0.0235	0.0299	0.8	0†	46.1 M	184.4
SAM2+LoRA (ours)	0.2184	0.2466	5.4	11.74 M†	46.1 M	184.4

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Quantitative Comparison

Table I presents the main results. SAM2+LoRA achieves the highest IoU (0.2184) and Dice (0.2466), outperforming both supervised baselines. DeepLabV3+ ranks second (IoU = 0.1849), benefiting from its ImageNet-pretrained backbone and multi-scale ASPP features. U-Net achieves IoU = 0.0857, limited by learning from scratch on only 940 images. Zero-shot SAM2 (IoU = 0.0235) confirms the domain gap between natural images and industrial defects is too large to bridge without adaptation.

Speed vs. accuracy. U-Net and DeepLabV3+ achieve near real-time FPS (47.3 and 43.7), suitable for online inspection lines. SAM2+LoRA at 5.4 FPS is adequate for offline inspection pipelines. SAM2 zero-shot at 0.8 FPS is impractically slow due to grid-based mask generation.

Parameter efficiency. SAM2+LoRA outperforms two fully-supervised models while training 2.6 \times fewer parameters than U-Net and 3.4 \times fewer than DeepLabV3+ (trainable parameters only; Table I explicitly separates trainable from total model parameters). This matters where labelled data is scarce and retraining costs are high.

B. Training Dynamics

SAM2+LoRA shows rapid early learning: val IoU = 0.2497 at epoch 10, converging to 0.2597 by epoch 30. U-Net starts near zero (val IoU = 0.0017 at epoch 10), consistent with learning visual representations from scratch on a small dataset. DeepLabV3+ leverages pretrained features for faster early convergence but still adapts slowly to industrial defect textures.

C. Qualitative Analysis and Grad-CAM

Fig. 1 shows predictions and Grad-CAM overlays for three representative defect types from the test set, revealing striking qualitative differences in how each paradigm attends to defect regions.

Row 1 (Crack). U-Net produces a large false-positive blob; its Grad-CAM shows diffuse purple activation spread uniformly across vertical texture patterns in the background, indicating the model has not learned crack-specific representations on 940 training images. DeepLabV3+ localises more correctly but Grad-CAM reveals broad blue-green activation covering non-defect regions. SAM2+LoRA produces a clean, thin segmentation precisely tracing the crack boundary.

Row 2 (Blowhole). U-Net completely misses the defect (all-black prediction); U-Net Grad-CAM is uniformly purple across the entire image, confirming total failure to localise. DeepLabV3+ Grad-CAM shows red-orange activation but covering an excessively large region with false activations. SAM2+LoRA correctly identifies the small blowhole with a tight segmentation.

Row 3 (Break/Fray). U-Net produces scattered false positives across the lower region. DeepLabV3+ Grad-CAM shows blue-green activation spread widely beyond the actual defect boundary. SAM2+LoRA produces the cleanest prediction, precisely capturing the defect at the image boundary.

These results confirm that SAM2's pretrained multi-scale edge representations transfer effectively to industrial defects via LoRA, while convolutional networks trained on small datasets fail to learn defect-discriminative features.

Fig. 1. Grad-CAM / Feature Attribution — Industrial Defect Segmentation. Columns (left to right): Input image, Ground-truth mask, U-Net prediction, U-Net Grad-CAM, DeepLabV3+ prediction, DeepLabV3+ Grad-CAM, SAM2+LoRA prediction. Rows: Crack (top), Blowhole (middle), Break/Fray (bottom). Warm colours (red-orange) in Grad-CAM overlays indicate high activation; cool colours (blue-purple) indicate low activation. U-Net activates diffusely across background texture; DeepLabV3+ is more focused but produces false activations in defect-free regions; SAM2+LoRA precisely localises defect boundaries across all three defect types.

D. Discussion

Why does LoRA work? SAM2's image encoder, pretrained on 11 M diverse images, has learned multi-scale edge and texture representations that transfer to industrial defects. LoRA adapts only the mask decoder's attention projections, requiring far less labelled data than training from scratch.

Why does zero-shot fail? SAM2's automatic mask generator selects candidates by predicted IoU, calibrated for natural objects. Industrial defects are thin, low-contrast, and topologically dissimilar to SAM2's training distribution. Without domain adaptation, the generator consistently selects incorrect masks.

Limitations. (1) SAM2+LoRA processes one image at a time, limiting training throughput. (2) Test-time prompts are sampled from ground-truth masks; real deployment requires a detection module or human operator. (3) Dataset (1,344 images) is small; results may differ on larger benchmarks. (4) Binary segmentation only; multi-class defect segmentation is future work. (5) Results are single-run with fixed seed 42 due to compute constraints.

VI. CONCLUSION

We presented a systematic cross-paradigm comparison of industrial surface defect segmentation covering supervised specialist networks, zero-shot foundation model inference, and LoRA-based parameter-efficient adaptation. SAM2+LoRA achieves the best mIoU (0.2184) and Dice (0.2466), outperforming both U-Net and DeepLabV3+ while training only 25% of SAM2's parameters. Zero-shot SAM2 (IoU = 0.0235) confirms domain adaptation is essential for industrial imagery. Grad-CAM analysis reveals SAM2+LoRA produces the most precise defect localisation, with particular advantage on fine-grained defects such as cracks where convolutional networks trained on small datasets completely fail. These results position LoRA-based foundation model adaptation as a practical and data-efficient alternative to training supervised networks from scratch.

Future work includes: batched training for SAM2+LoRA, automatic prompt generation without ground-truth masks, multi-class defect segmentation, ablation of LoRA rank and prompt strategies, and cross-dataset generalisation from Magnetic Tile to NEU-Seg and Severstal Steel Defect datasets.

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